

Broadband Ultrasonic Focusing in Water Using a Trapped-Air PLA Parabolic Meta-Mirror

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Background, Motivation and Objective

Efficient acoustic focusing in water is essential for ultrasonic imaging, nondestructive testing, and underwater sensing. Conventional solutions often rely on curved transducers or phased arrays, increasing system complexity and cost. Recently, trapped-air acoustic metamaterials have demonstrated strong acoustic impedance mismatch with water, enabling enhanced wave manipulation and subwavelength imaging capabilities [1]. In this work, a parabolic mirror fabricated from PLA with trapped air inclusions is investigated as a compact passive reflector for broadband ultrasonic focusing in water.

Statement of Contribution/Methods

The reflected acoustic field is modeled using the impulse-response formulation $h(r, t)$ for a plane piston source reflecting from a curved surface [2]:

$$h(r, t) = \int_S \delta(t - R/c)/(2\pi R) dS \quad (1)$$

where R is the distance between the mirror element and observation point, c is the sound speed in water, and S is the reflecting surface. The mirror response is evaluated using COMSOL finite-element simulations with a planar pressure excitation. The main contribution is the introduction of trapped air cavities within a PLA reflector fabricated by additive manufacturing. The trapped air increases the acoustic impedance mismatch between the reflector and water, enabling efficient acoustic reflection. This approach overcomes the intrinsically low reflection of solid plastics in water and enables compact MRI-compatible acoustic meta-devices.

Results/Discussion

Simulations show that the trapped-air PLA parabolic mirror focuses ultrasonic waves in water, producing a concentrated focal region along the mirror axis with significant pressure amplification at the focus. The trapped air significantly increases acoustic impedance mismatch, improving reflection efficiency and focusing performance. The structure operates over a broad frequency range from 100 kHz to 5 MHz, demonstrating broadband ultrasonic focusing capability. These results suggest that trapped-air PLA mirrors can provide a compact and low-cost solution for underwater ultrasonic imaging and sensing applications.

Figure: Schematic and Comsol Simulation of Trapped Air Parabolic Reflector

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References

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